

European projects, heads or tails?

Experiences of the UCM-GRASIA research group

Juan Pavón Mestras
jpavon@fdi.ucm.es

Proyectos europeos y ERCs, ¿cara o cruz?, by Juan Pavón, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License

Proyectos europeos, ¿para qué?

- Buena financiación
 - Muy superior a la de proyectos nacionales
 - Gestión más flexible y sencilla ⇒ Apoyo de la Oficina Europea I+D UCM
 - Se puede contratar personal con salarios decentes
 - ... solo que son más difíciles de conseguir
- Colaboración internacional
 - Abre el abanico de colaboradores
 - Multi-disciplinariedad
 - Visión más amplia e innovadora
 - Hervidero de ideas nuevas
 - Base para desarrollo de nuevos productos
 - Internacionalización del grupo de investigación
 - ... aunque está el riesgo de que el consorcio no funcione bien
- Entorno propicio para formación de jóvenes investigadores
- Bien valorados en el CV

The UCM GRASIA Research Team

- Coordinators: Jorge Gómez Sanz & Juan Pavón
- 30 researchers (18 PhD) + postgraduate students & fellows
 - 7 IPs
 - 1 project manager
- Multidisciplinary:
 - Artificial intelligence
 - Software engineering
 - Communication and media sciences
 - Statistics
 - Social work
 - Health care

Past profile of the group

co-RRI: Collaborative Responsible Research and Innovation to co-create the Future that we all want

Towards co-RRI

- Combine the intelligence of 4 types of stakeholders (*quadruple helix*)
- Integration of social and economic innovations with technical research
- Involving citizens and stakeholders from the earliest stages of the project and throughout its development
- Issues oriented R&D
 - Economic and social impact of knowledge: sustainable development

- *Fostering a Transition towards Responsible Research and Innovation Systems*
 - Oct. 2015 - Mar. 2018
- **Goal:**
creating and implementing **knowledge arenas**
to support knowledge actors to **collectively set research agendas**
that respond effectively, efficiently and in **societally robust ways**
to **local manifestations of global challenges**

Contact person: Dr. Marian Deblonde /Unit Sustainable Materials Management /VITO NV /Boeretang 200, 2400 MOL, Belgium
Tel: +32/14 33 58 46 marian.deblonde@vito.be www.vito.be/english

Funded by the Horizon 2020
Framework programme of the European Union
(Grant Agreement Number 665906)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 665906. This communication reflects only the author's view and the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

UCM-GRASIA

European projects

7

FoTTRIS Co-RRi concept

- **RRi:** a dynamic, **iterative process** in which **all stakeholders** in research and innovation become **mutually responsive** and share responsibility **for both the process and its outcomes**
 - Making science and technology more ethical, sustainable and socially beneficial
[A practical guide to Responsible Research and Innovation. Key lessons from RRI Tools. RRI Tools Coordination Team (2016)]
- **Co-RRi:**
 - **Co-definition** of what is conceived to be a 'solution' to a 'challenge' (e.g. resource scarcities)
 - **Co-analysing** the (causes and reasons) of/for the existence/persistence of the challenge
 - **Co-selection** of relevant theoretical, technological and practical knowledge and relevant research questions
 - **Co-design** of a research and innovation project
⇒ *Supported by web-based P2P tools*

UCM-GRASIA

European projects

8

How to co-RRi

COOKBOOK

HOW
TO CO-CREATE
RRI PROJECTS

5 steps for co-RRI projects conception

STEP 1: STARTER
(goal setting)

STEP 2: SOUP
(system mapping)

STEP 3: MAIN DISH
(visioning)

STEP 4: DESSERT
(project concept design)

STEP 5: LIQUEUR
(outreach)

FoTRRIS Transition Experiments

- Testing and validation of FoTRRIS concepts and collaborative tools
- Transition experiments in 5 countries on different subjects:
 - Austria: food shortage
 - Belgium: shortage of materials
 - Hungría: ciudades en transición
 - Italy: responsible energy consumption
 - **Spain: women and disability**
 - **Spain: the refugee crisis**

H2020 RISEWISE
Rise Women with disabilities
In Social Engagement

H2020 RAISD
Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively
vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

- 1 UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID Spain
- 2 CESIE Italy
- 3 UNIMED - UNIONE DELLE UNIVERSITA DEL MEDITERRANEO Italy
- 4 HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO Finland
- 5 Menedek Migransokat Segito Egyesulet Hungary
- 6 ANADOLU UNIVERSITY Turkey
- 7 YARMOUK UNIVERSITY Jordan
- 8 Lebanese International University Lebanon

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

⇒ Effective strategies of attention and inclusion must adapt to specific contexts of vulnerability through the active participation of those directly involved

ARU = Action Research Unit
TAIS = Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategy

Rise Women with disabilities In Social Engagement

Fair and inclusive twin transitions for a stronger social Europe

Distributed Autonomous Organizations

- ERC Starting Grant: P2P MODELS
 - Towards a new **collaborative economy**
 - **Decentralizing power and value using blockchain**

European projects evaluation process

Evaluation criteria

1. Excellence

- Ground-breaking nature (eg. level of ambition, beyond the state-of-the-art, novel approach, addresses challenge, ...)
- Conceptually robust; trans-disciplinarity, ...

2. Impact [...] extent to which project outputs contribute to:

- The expected impacts listed in the work programme under the relevant topic;
- Enhancing innovation capacity and integration of new knowledge;
- Strengthening the competitiveness and growth of companies by developing innovations meeting the needs of European and global markets;
- Effectiveness of the proposed measures to communicate the project, disseminate and/or exploit the project results, and appropriate management of IPR.

3. Quality and efficiency of implementation

- Coherence and effectiveness of the work plan, including appropriateness of the allocation of tasks and resources;
- Competences, experience and complementarity of the individual participants, as well as of the consortium as a whole;
- Appropriateness of the management structures and procedures, including risk management

⇒ **Ver con detenimiento el Application Form template**

Evaluation criteria

1. Excellence

- **Long-term vision:**
 - How convincing is the vision of a radically new technology towards which the project would contribute in the long term?
- **Science-towards-technology breakthrough:**
 - How concrete, novel and ambitious is the proposed **science-towards-technology breakthrough** with respect to the **state-of-the-art**?
 - What **advancement** does it provide towards realising the envisioned technology?
- **Objectives:**
 - How **concrete** and **plausible** are the proposed objectives?
 - To what extent is the **high-risk/high-gain** research approach appropriate for achieving them?
 - How sound is the proposed **methodology**, including the underlying concepts, models, assumptions, alternative directions and options, appropriate consideration of the **gender dimension** in research content, and the quality of **open science practices**?
- **Interdisciplinarity:**
 - How relevant is the interdisciplinary approach from traditionally distant disciplines for achieving the proposed breakthrough?

Evaluation criteria

2. Impact [...] extent to which project outputs contribute to:

- **Long-term impact:**
 - How significant are the potential transformative positive effects that the envisioned new technology would have to our **economy, environment and society**?
- **Innovation potential:**
 - How adequate are the proposed measures for protection of results and any other exploitation measures to facilitate future translation of research results into innovations?
 - How suitable are the proposed measures for involving and empowering key actors that have the potential to take the lead in translating research into innovations in the future?
- **Communication and Dissemination:**
 - How suitable are the measures to maximise expected outcomes and impacts, including communication activities, for raising awareness about the project results' potential to establish new markets and/or address global challenges?

Evaluation criteria

3. Quality and efficiency of implementation

- **Work plan:**
 - How **coherent** and **effective** are the work plan (work packages, tasks, deliverables, milestones, timeline, etc.) and **risk mitigation** measures in order to achieve the project objectives?
- **Allocation of resources:**
 - How appropriate and effective is the allocation of resources (comprising person-months and other cost items) to work packages and consortium members?
- **Quality of the consortium:**
 - To what extent do the consortium members have all the necessary **high-quality expertise** for performing the project tasks?

Preparation of a proposal

Consortio equilibrado y con partners experimentados

Ojo con las tareas en que nos involucramos

Propiedad intelectual y explotación de resultados

Proyectos europeos - Recomendaciones

- Empezar a trabajar la propuesta desde el momento en que se empieza a hablar de la convocatoria
- El proyecto debe **ceñirse a la descripción de la call**. Analizar palabra a palabra su contenido
- Necesario definir con antelación los **objetivos** del proyecto y el reparto de **tareas** ⇒ Sobre esto se construye el consorcio
- Escribir bajo la perspectiva de una propuesta ganadora
⇒ **Todos los detalles son importantes**
- Trabajar muy bien el **estado del arte**
⇒ Explicar muy bien porqué el proyecto va más allá
- Memoria **comprensible**: qué, porqué, cómo, quién, para qué
- No abrir excesivamente el campo de aplicación con muchos objetivos y muchos desarrollos ⇒ dificulta la comprensión de la memoria
- Posibilidad de implantación e **impacto** a nivel europeo

Participant portal

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home>

Funding & tender opportunities
Single Electronic Data Interchange Area (SEDIA)

SEARCH FUNDING & TENDERS

HOW TO PARTICIPATE

PROJECTS & RESULTS

WORK AS AN EXPERT

SUPPORT

Find calls for proposals and tenders

Search calls for proposals and tenders by keywords, programmes...

Search

EU Programmes

Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF)

Border Management and Visa Instrument (BMVI)

Customs Control Equipment Instrument (CCEI)

Connecting Europe Facility (CEF)

Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values Programme (CERV)

Creative Europe (CREA)

Customs Programme (CUST)

Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL)

Europe Direct (ED)

European Defence Fund (EDF)

European Parliament (EP)

EU Anti-fraud Programme (EUAF)

European Solidarity Corps (ESC)

Erasmus+ Programme (ERASMUS+)

European Social Fund + (ESF)

European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF)

Euratom Research and Training Programme (EURATOM)

Fiscalis Programme (FISC)

European Commission Experts

https://commission.europa.eu/jobs-european-commission/experts_en

EN English

Search

Home > Jobs at the European Commission > Become an expert at the European Commission

Experts

How to become an expert for the European Commission. General qualifications required, roles available and where to register your interest.

Register to work as an expert

EU institutions appoint external experts to assist in the evaluation of grant applications, projects and tenders, and to provide opinions and advice in specific cases.

Rules for experts evaluating tenders

The European Commission appoints independent, external experts to evaluate tenders.

UCM-GRASIA

European projects

25

European Commission Experts

- **Evaluadores**
 - Evaluación de propuestas de las convocatorias (calls)
 - Modalidades: evaluador, rapporteur, chairperson, o vice-chairperson
- **Revisores**
 - Proyectos/Acciones en ejecución
- **Observadores**
 - Informan sobre la equidad del proceso de evaluación en todas sus fases
 - Comprueban que los expertos aplican correctamente los criterios de evaluación
- **Comités asesores de la CE**
 - Asistencia en la preparación, implementación y evaluación de programas y diseño de políticas
- **Miembros del ERC Scientific Council**

UCM-GRASIA

European projects

26

Quién puede ser elegido como experto

- **Experiencia** en investigación e innovación en cualquier campo científico
 - Incluyendo aspectos relacionados con la gestión
- Tener al menos un **título universitario**
- Estar disponible, ocasionalmente, por periodos de tiempo cortos
- Nivel de **inglés** aceptable
 - Lectura
 - Escritura: informes de evaluación
 - Hablado: consensus meetings, project review meetings

¿Por qué hacerse experto de la CE?

- Formación
 - Cómo se presentan los buenos proyectos
 - Cómo se evalúan los proyectos
 - Cómo funciona el sistema
- Actualización del estado del arte
 - Qué se está haciendo y quién
- Ampliación de nuestra red social
 - Durante las evaluaciones se conoce a otros expertos
 - Y a personal de la Comisión Europea
- Remuneración

Condiciones del contrato de evaluador (H2020)

- En el contrato se fija el número de días de trabajo
 - Remote and Central evaluation (en casa y en el lugar de la revisión/evaluación)
 - Evaluaciones: Aprox. 3 días remote + 5 días central
 - Revisiones: 2 días remote + 1 día meeting
 - El número de días se computa según el número de evaluaciones
- Pagos
 - Dietas: 450 € por día
 - Dietas de alojamiento: 100 € (Bruselas)
 - Dietas de manutención: 92 € (Bruselas)
 - Gastos de transporte
 - Billete de avión en clase económica
 - Otros gastos de transporte (excl. taxi)

Ética del experto

- Conflicto de interés
 - Involucrado en una propuesta
 - Beneficiado directamente
 - Muy relacionado con participante
 - Direct/Indirect conflict of interest
- Confidencialidad
- Equidad, Objetividad
- Ante cualquier duda/conflict of interest contactar al responsable (project officer, vice-chair, etc.)

Recomendaciones para rellenar el perfil de experto

- Seleccionar todos los programas apropiados para el perfil
- En idiomas el fundamental es el **inglés**
- Educación: lo importante es el grado de doctor
- Área de experiencia: ajustar la experiencia personal a las áreas del programa marco
 - Importante indicar en **Open keywords** palabras que se mencionen en el programa y los objetivos de las convocatorias
- Experiencia profesional: información que demuestre la experiencia en las áreas indicadas
 - Importante el resumen de experiencia en Employment history
 - Es importante la experiencia en la **industria** (se pregunta explícitamente)
 - Experience in Field: previa en programas de la UE
 - Añadir otros: paneles de revisión por pares (ANEP, ...) y congresos/revistas
 - Publications: asociar palabras clave apropiadas a las áreas de experiencia con las publicaciones
 - Achievements: patentes, productos resultado de la I+D
 - Additional info: logros relevantes del curriculum

ERC

- **Starting Grants** (1,5 M€)
 - 2-7 años después de lectura de tesis
 - posibilidad de restar 18 meses/hijo en caso de maternidad
- **Consolidator Grants** (2 M€)
 - 8-12 años después de lectura de tesis
 - posibilidad de restar 18 meses/hijo en caso de maternidad
- **Advanced Grants** (2,5 M€)
 - sin requisitos (investigadores “senior”)
⇒ 5 años

+ 0,5 / 1 / 1,5 M€ para compra de equipo / acceso a instalaciones

European Research Council

Established by the European Commission

**BLUE SKY
RESEARCH**

*The ERC encourages in particular proposals that **cross disciplinary boundaries**, pioneering ideas that address **new and emerging fields** and applications that introduce **unconventional, innovative approaches***

Ground-breaking nature - Potential impact - Scientific excellence

Conclusions

- In all proposals:
 - Address **ALL points**
 - Talk to your European R&D Office and **National Contact Points**
 - **Review** by as many people and diversity as possible (generalists and specialists)
 - Cooperation with different actors (4-helix)
 - Risk of bias by working only with those who share the same interests and views
- In ERC and MCSA, the **CV** is essential
 - It must be prepared, especially for Starting Grants
- In other European projects the personal CV is not very important, but the team (and institution) and the **balance of the consortium** is important
- A **co-RRI** approach helps
 - More original and innovative proposals
 - Real impact, applicable and useful technological solutions
 - Improved involvement of the working team

<http://grasia.fdi.ucm.es>